

Hydrogeochemical Assessment and Quality Management of Groundwater in Aizawl District, Mizoram: Implications for Sustainable Utilization in a Sub-Tropical Climate

Krista Lalnarammawia^{1*}, P. Anandhan², BibiShyn W.K¹, R. Manivannan²

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Earth Sciences, Annamalai University Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram. Tamil Nadu, India.

² Assistant Professor, Department of Earth Sciences, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram. Tamil Nadu, India.

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Abstract

An all-encompassing strategy founded in hydrogeochemistry was chosen to establish the quality-oriented utilisation of water in the study area of Aizawl District in the northern part of Mizoram. The study areas fall in a sub-tropical climate which shows that it receives a high amount of rainfall in a year. Aizawl district falls under the Surma group of sedimentary terrain represented by sandstones, siltstones, and shales. The samples were collected from 60 locations across the study area for two seasons. The study area's groundwater is neutral to alkaline, with higher pH concentrations during PRM and lower in POM. Most samples fall within WHO's permissible drinking water quality limits, except for HCO_3^- and K^+ , which exceed during PRM. The water is mostly suitable for drinking and domestic use, with $\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{Cl}$ dominating anions and $\text{Ca} + \text{Mg}$ dominating cations. The majority of samples fall in C_1S_1 , indicating low salinity and sodium hazards. The water is good to moderate for irrigation purposes, with Gibbs boomerang indicating the weathering dominant zone. Modified Piper diagrams show high $\text{Ca} + \text{Mg}$ and $\text{SO}_4 + \text{Cl}$ fields, with little gypsum contamination. The overall water quality meets WHO standards for drinking and domestic use and is suitable for irrigation purposes.

Keywords: Hydrogeochemistry, Aizawl district, pre-monsoon, southwest monsoon, water quality.

1. Introduction

Water is essential for human existence, particularly the quality of water, which is of utmost importance for mankind as it is directly associated with human health and well-being. Water is prominently sourced from rivers which support many livelihoods for mankind (Ayogu et al. 2020). The quality of groundwater is determined by its chemical and physical characteristics, which are altered by the soluble substances produced by weathering, decomposition, and other associated processes that occur over time and distance. Understanding these factors is crucial for evaluating the suitability of groundwater for different purposes and for formulating efficient management tactics. Groundwater quality is primarily influenced by the quality of recharged water, atmospheric precipitation, inland surface water, and subsurface geochemical processes (Singaraja et al. 2014).

Over the past few decades, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of maintaining high standards of groundwater quality (Anandhan et al. 2023). This increased awareness can be attributed to the negative effects of industrialisation, rapid urbanisation, unregulated land-use practices, population growth, and intensive agricultural methods, all of which contribute to the risk of soil and groundwater contamination (Etikala et al. 2019). For sustainable water resource management, it is crucial to understand the geochemical properties of groundwater in this specific environment. The geochemical analysis provides insights into the processes that control the quality of groundwater, such as rock-water interactions, dissolution of minerals, ion exchange, and human activities like agriculture and industrial discharge (Johnson et al. 2011). Evaluating these factors aids in determining the drinkability of groundwater, its suitability for irrigation, and its possible effects on infrastructure due to processes such as scaling and corrosion. Additionally, assessing key agrochemical indicators such as nitrate and fluoride levels is crucial, as these substances have been shown to contribute significantly to non-carcinogenic health risks among both children and adults within affected populations (Shukla & Saxena, 2020). Furthermore, prevailing research indicates that a considerable proportion of groundwater samples exceed safety thresholds for nitrates, particularly posing heightened risks to children compared to adults, thereby underscoring the necessity for rigorous monitoring and management strategies to ensure potable water quality and mitigate potential health hazards (Barakat et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2021; Shukla & Saxena, 2020). When choosing sampling sites, it is important to take into account factors such as the type of rock and soil, the shape and structure of the land, the distance to nearby bodies of water, and the impact of urban and agricultural practices.

Aizawl, the capital city of Mizoram, India, is located within the Tlawng River basin, which experiences significant seasonal variations in water availability (Lalhmingliana et al., 2020). The region, which is a part of the Himalayan Mountain range, is characterised by an intricate geological formation, precipitous inclines, and a substantial concentration of waterways. The combination of these factors, along with the growing human-induced pressures, has resulted in a decrease in the quantity and quality of both surface and groundwater resources in the region (Biswas & Azyu, 2021). Previous research has emphasised the significant water management difficulties encountered in the Tlawng River basin, which include the necessity of locating appropriate sites for building water reservoirs availability (Lalhmingliana et al., 2020). Nevertheless, there is a lack of research on the socio-ecological factors related to water resources and their management in the rural regions of Mizoram (Biswas & Azyu, 2021). This study aims to address this research gap by conducting a comprehensive assessment of groundwater resources in the four different block of Aizawl district, a primarily rural area. This case study focuses on the determination of the utility of groundwater in Aizawl District, with a detailed analysis of its geochemical parameters. By examining the spatial distribution and seasonal variations of these parameters, we aim to identify the factors influencing groundwater quality and to evaluate its suitability for drinking, irrigation, and industrial purposes. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights for policymakers, water resource managers, and local communities in making informed decisions about groundwater utilization and conservation.

This lack of information has made the examination of the water quality of important significance, as it will provide essential insights into the hydrogeochemical processes occurring in the study area, including both natural and anthropogenic components (Biswas & Azyu, 2021). The analysis will be based on criteria such as sodium percentage (Na%), sodium adsorption ratio, residual sodium carbonate, and total hardness of the water samples. The current study intends to assess the quality of groundwater and determine its utility. Additionally, it seeks to identify the primary geochemical processes and their evolution over time in the studied area.

1.1 *Study area*

The Aizawl district is situated in the northeastern region of Mizoram geographical extension 23°18'24.04" N to 24°24'47.23 N latitudes and 92°37'27.62" E to 93°02'26.71" E longitudes with an average around 1,132 metres (3,714 feet) above mean sea level. It covers

an area of 2138.62 sq. km. Geologically, the Mizo hills are classified as a segment of the Rakhine (Arakan) Mountains. These mountains consist of a sequence of closely spaced ridges oriented in a north-south direction. They are mostly composed of sandstone, limestone, and shale, all of which are Cenozoic rock formations. The elevation divided by the slender river valleys, ascends to around 2100 meters (CGWB, 2022). The study area exhibits a range of climates, from moist tropical to moist sub-tropical. The study area (Fig. 1), which is Aizawl district experiences the phenomenal influence of the South West Tropical monsoon, which occurs from May to October, accompanied by intermittent winter rainfall with an average annual rainfall consistently measured at 2794 mm with minimal fluctuation around the entire region. The average monsoon rainfall recorded is 1761 mm, accounting for 63% of the total rainfall, while the non-monsoon rainfall is 1033 mm, making up 37% of the total (CGWB, 2022).

Fig 1. Sample location and study area map.

1.2 Drainage

The predominant drainage pattern, characterised by varying bifurcation ratios, adheres to the north-south trending depressions and gorges within the low-lying topography, which are interspersed with elevated terrain. The depressions and gorges are, in most instances, the physiographic representations of the defects and additional structural patterns. The tributaries and streamlets form ‘angular’, ‘sub-parallel’ to ‘parallel’ and ‘dendritic’ drainage pattern (GSI, 2011). The drainage gradient is generally moderate. The steep hills are divided by rivers that

flow north or south, forming deep gorges between the ranges. The state contains countless rivers, streams, and brooks. In the north, the Tlawng (Dhaleswari), the Tuirail (Sonai) and the Tuivawl start from the middle of Mizoram and flowing north fall in the Barak River in Cachar district. In the south, the Karnafuli flows north from the southern tip of the state and from near Demagiri in West Central Mizoram, it flows to Bangladesh where it has been tapped for a massive hydel project (GSI, 2011).

1.3 Hydrogeology

Geologically the area is underlain by a repeat of arenaceous and argillaceous layers of sediment. The arenaceous and argillaceous group of rocks occurs in relatively higher and lower grounds, respectively. These have distorted into a sequence of anticlinal and synclinal folds ranging from NNW-SSE to NNE-SSW, where plunging orientation is either towards north or south (CGWB, 2022). Hydrogeologically, the diverse rock types found in Mizoram can be divided into two groups i.e. semi-consolidated and unconsolidated formations.

The semi-consolidated rocks developed secondary porosity due to tectonic disturbances. At the same time, unconsolidated formations with limited alluvial thickness are restricted near streams and rivers. The entire district is occupied by hills and slopes typically more than 20%, thus the rainwater flows out as surface runoff. Groundwater storage is limited to largely secondary porosity and structural control in the higher-elevation aquifers in this terrain. These aquifers are the major source of springs. Groundwater held in the hill slopes is emitted in the form of springs, which are being used as a source of water supply.

Groundwater exploration carried out by CGWB (2022) reveals that the yield potential of deep tube wells within the depth range of 200 m tapping Tertiary sandstone ranges from 120 to 330 litres per minute for a drawdown of 13 to 20 m. The transmissivity ranges from 11 to 46 m²/day.

1.4 Geology

La-Touche (1891) was the earliest explorer in Mizoram and discovered that the region comprises extensive flysch facies of shale and sandstone, which are folded in a north-south direction. Afterwards, the rocks in the centre region of Northern Mizoram are delineated and categorised in the Surma series into the Bhuban and Bokabil Stages. The rocks were subjected to compressional forces, resulting in folds forming longitudinal anticlinal hills and narrow synclinal valleys (Munshi, 1963). The regional geology of the plotted area displays a repeating

succession of Neogene sedimentary rocks from the Surma Group and Tipam Formation. These sequences are structured into a series of about north-south orientated longitudinally dipping anticlines. Synclines. The litho-units contain primarily sandstone, siltstone and shale. The topographical representation of the region often conveys rather strong clues about their lithology. The arenaceous and argillaceous categories of rocks occupy relatively higher and lower grounds correspondingly (GSI, 2011).

Surma basin situated in the eastern proximity of India is also characterized by a thick sedimentary column which can be considered as the northeastern extension of the Greater Bengal basin. This basin was initiated due to the mutual collision between Indian and Burmese Plate. Due to this collision, the bedrock has experienced folding which is aligned with N-S trending hill ranges. The basin was also carved by a variety of parallel to sub-parallel transverse faults and thrusts. The litho association consists of sandstone, siltstone, and shale and their varied proportions (Bharali et al., 2017).

1.5 Anthropogenic activities

According to the Mizoram Pollution Control Board, the main sources of water pollution in the Aizawl district are domestic wastes, chemical fertilizers used in agricultural activities, waste discharge by motor workshops etc. Since there is no wastewater treatment system in the State, wastewater is let off everywhere that progressively reaches the rivers and streams damaging the water supply. Since there are no large-scale industries, industrial water contamination is almost negligible.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Sample collection and procedures

Both groundwater and surface water were collected from 60 different locations during pre-monsoon (January-February) and Southwest-Monsoon (July-August) of the year 2023. Sampling locations were recorded with the help of GPS instruments. A sample bottle of 1L capacity was used to collect the water sample and tightly seal it to prevent evaporation. The sample bottles were labelled accordingly and carried to the laboratory for analysis. pH and EC were measured in the field with a hand-held (Konvio near) pH and EC meter. All the chemical parameters were analyzed by the recommended method of the American Public Health Association (APHA, 1998). The cations Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were analysed using the EDTA titration technique. The Titrimetry method was used to measure anions such as Cl^- and HCO_3^- . Sodium

ions (Na^{2+}) and potassium ions (K^+) were determined using the flame photometer technique. Nitrate (NO_3^-) and fluoride (F^-) were determined using a spectrophotometric technique (Chakraborty et al., 2022). Sulphate (SO_4^-), dissolved silica (H_2SO_4) and Phosphate (PO_4^-) were analyzed using UV-vis double beam spectrophotometry (Eaton, 1950). Sulphate was measured using the standard turbidity method with a conditioning reagent (Glycerol, HCl, Ethyl alcohol), and turbidity was monitored at 420 nm following the addition of BaCl_2 . Phosphate was measured using the ortho-phosphate method at 880 nm. Dissolved silica was determined using the molybdo-silicate technique at a wavelength of 810 nm. Except for pH and EC, all the concentrations expressed in mg/L. The study area map was generated using Arcmap 10.8.2. The collected data was utilised to determine the sodium absorption ratio (SAR), residual sodium carbonate (RSC), sodium percentage (Na %), permeability index (PI), corrosive ratio (CR), and hardness by WATCLAST (Chidambaram et al., 2003). Aquachem Software v.4 was also used for Wilcox diagram (Wilcox, 1995). Piper for classification based on the water chemistry was obtained using Aquachem Software v.4.

3. Result

3.1 Hydrogeochemistry

The chemistry data presented in Figure 2 includes illustrations of statistical parameters such as maximum, minimum, and average during PRM and SWM. The water in the research area is neutral to alkaline, with a pH range from 6.01 to 9.92, with an average of 7.16 during PRM and 6.10 to 8.10 with an average of 6.89 during SWM. The maximum value was recorded in the centre of the research area. Electrical Conductivity (EC) results range from 23 to 825 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with an average value of 274.09 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ during PRM and 31 – 835 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with an average value of 295 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The research area demonstrated elevated concentrations, signifying efficient ion leaching into the groundwater system during recharge (Masood et al., 2024). During the pre-monsoon season (PRM), the TDS values range from 151.79 to 713.70 mg/l, with an average of 310.91 mg/l. During the Southwest Monsoon (SWM), the values fluctuate between 103.76 and 429.58 mg/l, with an average of 235.60 mg/l.

Fig 2. Box Plot for the maximum, minimum and average of the chemical constituents in groundwater during PRM (A) and SWM (B) (all values in mg/l except pH).

The maximum, minimum and average concentrations of the ions show that most of the samples fall above the average concentrations (Fig 2). There is a broad range of ion concentrations, especially with PO₄⁻ and NO₃⁻. The study indicates that the concentrations of PO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, and Na⁺ in the majority of samples are below the average value in both seasons. Calcium concentration ranges from 24.0 to 56.0 mg/l during PRM with an average value of

36.03 mg/l. During SWM, the value ranges from 20.0 to 46.0 mg/l with an average of 28.23 mg/l, which shows the decrease in concentration during southwest monsoon. Magnesium concentration ranges from 9.0 to 22.2 mg/l during PRM and 6.2 to 24.2 mg/l during SWM with an average of 15.85 mg/l and 9.86 mg/l, respectively. Na^+ has a wide range from 0.9 to 60.7 mg/l during PRM with an average value of 17.0 and 1.2 to 57.5 mg/l during SWM with an average of 12.20 mg/l. Cl^- concentrations in the study area range from 26.58 to 168.38 mg/l with an average value of 54.52 mg/l during PRM. During SWM the chloride concentration ranged from 21.2 to 124.07 mg/l with averages of 53.84 mg/l. HCO_3^- concentration ranges from 58.6 to 347.10 mg/l during PRM with an average of 114.50 mg/l, while during SWM the concentration ranges from 13.4 to 152.3 mg/l with an average of 56.30 mg/l. SO_4^{2-} value range in the study area from 0.77 to 20.69 mg/l with an average of 5.03 mg/l during PRM. In SWM, the value ranges from 0.06 to 15.1 mg/l with an average of 2.98 mg/l. PO_4^- with a value ranging from 0.3 to 52.60 mg/l with an average of 4.44 mg/l during PRM. During SWM the concentration of PO_4^- varies from 0.38 to 11.58 mg/l with an average value of 1.56 mg/l. NO_3^- and F^- have a concentration ranging from 0.01 to 19.5 mg/l and 0.01 to 1.2 mg/l during PRM respectively. During SWM the concentration ranges from 0.01 to 18.92 mg/l and 0.01 to 1.43 mg/l with an average of 4.63 mg/l and 0.18 mg/l for both NO_3^- and F^- . The concentration of silica ranges from 4.8 to 138.6 mg/l during PRM and 2.6 to 166.4 mg/l during SWM. The average concentration of silica for PRM and SWM are 55.10 mg/l and 62.67 mg/l respectively.

3.2 Classification based on water use criteria for drinking purposes.

The suitability of water for various uses, including as drinking, industrial applications, domestic needs, and irrigation, is evaluated due to extensive developmental activities, including over-extraction and the infiltration of agricultural and industrial effluents into the groundwater system. This has emphasised the classification of groundwater based on its value for multiple purposes. Drinking water standards are determined by the presence of undesirable tastes, odours, or colours, as well as compounds that may have detrimental physiological effects. The portability of drinking water primarily depends on the recommended limits for specific factors. When water is above the allowable threshold, it becomes unsuitable for human consumption (WHO, 1993). Variations in water quality and its suitability for irrigation and domestic usage have been discussed by Alaya et al. (2013), Anoop et al. (2021), Aragaw and Gnanachandrasamy (2021) and Shrestha and Kazama (2006). Classification of groundwater was attempted by Anadhan et al. (2016) and Paramaguru et al. (2016) suggesting groundwater

suitability for drinking and public health. Quality assessment of potable water was done by Kumar et al. (2009) in Kolasib district, Mizoram, and a geospatial-based study of water quality in Aizawl district was done by Lalnarammawia, Krista & Paluchamy, Anandhan (2024).

Table 2 shows the range of ionic concentration in water chemistry of the study area and the prescribed specification World Health Organization (WHO, 2011). The majority of the samples fall within the permissible limit of WHO with few locations exceeding the limit.

Table 2. Comparison of water quality with standards WHO (2011)

Parameters	WHO (2011)	Study area ranges		% of the sample exceeds the permissible limit	
		PRM	SWM	PRM	SWM
pH	6.5-8.5	6.01-9.92	6.10-8.10	15	30
TDS	1000	151.79-713.70	103.76-429.58	0	0
EC	1400	23-825	31-835	0	0
Ca	100	24.0-56.0	20.0-46.0	0	0
Mg	50	9.0-22.20	6.2-24.2	0	0
Na	200	0.9-60.7	1.2-57.5	0	0
K	20	0.1-20.5	0.1-18.3	1	0
Cl	250	26.58-168.38	21.2-124.07	0	0
HCO ₃	300	58.6-347.10	13.4-152.3	5	0
SO ₄	200	0.77-20.69	0.06-15.1	0	0
NO ₃	50	0.01-19.5	0.01-11.58	0	0
F	1.5	0.01-1.2	0.01-1.43	0	0

The pH is one of the important parameters of water quality, with a few samples (15%) above and below the permissible limit during PRM and 30 % during SWM. K⁻ exceeds concentration exceeds the permissible limit during PRM. Most of the samples are within the permissible limit, and a few samples exceed the permissible limit for HCO₃⁻.

3.3 Classification of water use for irrigation purposes.

The utility of groundwater for irrigation purposes is generally dependent upon factors such as soil texture and composition, crops planted and irrigation procedures in addition to the chemical characteristics of the water. The quality of irrigation water is determined by the estimation of parameters such as Na %, SAR, RSC, Wilcox (1995), PI, residual sodium bicarbonate, magnesium hazard (MH), Kelly's ratio and potential salinity (PS).

Na % Eaton (1950) classification shows that almost 100% falls in safe category during PRM and SWM (Table 3). Also, Na% Wilcox (1995) classification shows that 65% fall in excellent category, 23% fall in good category and 12% fall in permissible limit during Pre-monsoon. During southwest monsoon 60% fall in excellent category, 35% fall in good and 5% fall in permissible limit. Residual Sodium Carbonate (RSC) Richard (1954) is an index, which indicates the Sodium Hazards. In RSC 98% and 100% of the PRM and SWM sample fall in good category respectively, and 2% of the PRM sample fall in medium category (Table 3). Hardness refers to the interaction with soap and the subsequent production of scale. It elevates the boiling point and does not adversely affect human health. In the study area 62% and 92% of the sample fall in slightly hard category during PRM and SWM respectively. 38% and 8% of the sample fall in moderately hard category during PRM and SWM (Table 3).

Table 3. Result of WATCLAST computer program for PRM and SWM (Chidambaram et al., 2003).

Category	Grade	PRM n= 60	SWM n= 60	Category	Grade	PRM n= 60	SWM n= 60	Category	PRM n= 60	SWM n= 60	
Na % Wilcox (1995)				USGS Hardness				TDS Classification			
Excellent	0 – 20	39	36	Soft	<75	0	0	<200	2	16	
Good	20 – 40	14	21	Slightly Hard	75 – 150	37	55	200-500	55	44	
Permissible	40 – 60	7	3	Moderately Hard	150 – 300	23	5	500-1500	3	0	
Doubtful	60 – 80	0	0	Very Hard	>150	0	0	1500-3000	0	0	
Unsuitable	>80	0	0	IBE Schoeller (1965)				Cation Facies			
Na % Eaton (1950)				(Na + K) rock-> Ca/Mg gm.				Ca-Mg Facies			
Safe	<60	60	60	(Na + K) gm.-> Ca/Mg rock				Ca-Na Facies			
Unsafe	>60	0	0	Schoeller Classification (1967)				Na-Ca Facies			
S. A. R. Richards (1854)				Type I				Na Facies			
Excellent	0 – 10	60	60	Type II				Anion Facies			
Good	10 – 18	0	0	Type III				HCO₃ Facies			
Fair	18 – 26	0	0	Type IV				HCO₃-Cl-SO₄ Facies			
Poor	>26	0	0	Corrosivity Ratio (1990)				Cl-SO₄-HCO₃ Facies			
R. S. C. Richards (1954)				Safe				Cl Facies			
Good	<1.25	59	60	Unsafe				Hardness Classification (Handa, 1964)			
Medium	1.25 – 2.5	1	0	Chloride Classification (Stuyfzand, 1989)				Permanent Hardness (NCH)			
Bad	>2.5	0	0	Extremely Fresh				A1			
EC Wilcox (1955)				Very Fresh				A2			
Excellent	<250	46	45	Fresh				A3			
Good	250 – 750	11	13	Fresh Brackish				Temporary Hardness (CH)			
Permissible	750 – 2250	3	2	Brackish				B1			
Doubtful	2250 – 5000	0	0	Brackish-salt				B2			
Unsuitable	>5000	0	0	Salt				B3			
				Hyperhaline							

The Styfzands classification Stuyfzand (1959), predicated on chloride concentration in samples, reveals that 20% of the samples are categorised as extremely fresh, 78% as fresh, and 2% as fresh brackish during PRM. In SWM, 7% of the sample is classified as very fresh, while 93% is categorised as fresh (Table 3). Higher concentration during PRM may be due to a longer residence time of groundwater in hist rock (Bolarinwa, 2017).

The Wilcox classification of groundwater for irrigation purposes was applied by United State Salinity USSL, (1954) laboratory to obtain the classification of irrigation water. The diagram shows that during PRM, the majority of the samples fall in C₁-C₂ category indicating low to medium salinity hazard and a few samples fall in C₃ with high salinity hazards (Fig 3). During SWM mostly the samples fall in C₁-C₂ with minimal sample fall in C₂ (Fig 4). Figure 3 illustrates that the majority of the groundwater samples fall in C₁S₁ category representing low salinity and low sodium hazards with a few samples fall in C₂S₁ indicating medium salinity and low sodium hazards during PRM. Figure 4 shows that during SWM majority of the samples fall in C₁S₁ category representing low salinity and low sodium hazards with a few samples falling in C₂S₁ indicating medium salinity and low sodium hazards.

Fig.3. USSL classification for groundwater (PRM).

Fig.4. USSL classification for groundwater (SWM).

The permeability index is an important characteristic which determines the quality of irrigation water, in connection to soil for development in agriculture. Based on the permeability index, Doneen (1948) classified groundwater as Class I, Class II and Class II to find out the suitability of groundwater for irrigation applications. Figure 5 represents Doneen’s plot for irrigation water during PRM showing that the majority of samples fall in Class I and Class II, which indicates the water in the study area is good to moderate for irrigation purposes. During SWM the majority of samples fall into Class II and a few samples in Class I, indicating the water is moderate to good during southwest monsoon (Fig 6).

Fig.5. Doneen classification of irrigation water (PRM).

Fig.6. Doneen classification of irrigation water (SWM).

The Piper diagram shows (Piper, 1944) the migration of Ca-HCO₃ type during pre-monsoon to the Ca-Cl type during southwest monsoon (Fig. 7). The monsoon adds Cl⁻ to the groundwater by dissolution of ions and the process of weathering. Thereby, diluting the system and reducing the impact of HCO₃⁻ which is a dominant anion during pre-monsoon.

Fig.7. Piper diagram for groundwater during pre-monsoon and southwest monsoon.

The distribution of sample data points suggests that the chemical weathering of rock-forming minerals influences the groundwater quality during PRM and SWM (Gibbs, 1970). In general, the Gibbs plot reveals that the rock-water interaction is also a chief factor which controls the chemistry of groundwater in the study area (Fig.8). Minor representations in the evaporation zone may indicate a contribution from secondary leachates/ion contribution during PRM.

Fig.8. Gibbs plot for mechanism controlling water chemistry during PRM (A) and SWM (B).

In Johnson's (1975) plot most of the samples fall in Ca+Mg, SO₄+Cl and HCO₃+CO₃ dominant field and high Ca+Mg and SO₄+Cl field during PRM with a minimal sample fall in water contaminated with gypsum (Fig. 9). During SWM the sample fall in high Ca+Mg and

SO₄+Cl dominant field with few samples fall in Ca+Mg, SO₄+Cl and HCO₃+CO₃ field (Fig.10). In general, alkali exceeds alkaline, controlled by strong and weak acids.

Fig.9. Modified Johnson plots for the study area during pre-monsoon.

Fig.10. Modified Johnson plots for the study area during southwest monsoon.

4. Conclusion

The groundwater in the study area is neutral to alkaline, with a pH concentration higher during PRM and lower in POM. A few samples exhibit WHO standards for water quality for pH during both seasons. The ionic concentration in the study area shows that almost all the samples fall within the permissible limit for drinking water quality set by WHO, except for HCO_3^- and K^+ which exceed during PRM. This indicates that the groundwater sample in the study area is mostly fitted for drinking and domestic uses. $\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{Cl}$ dominates the anions and $\text{Ca} + \text{Mg}$ dominates the cation during PRM and SWM. USSL classification shows that the majority of the sample falls in C_1S_1 indicating low salinity and sodium hazards within the study area. Doneen's permeability index classification results show the sample mostly falls in Class I and II during PRM and SWM which indicates the water is good to moderate for irrigation uses. Gibbs boomerang shows that the majority of samples fall in the weathering dominant zone in both seasons which controls the water chemistry. Modified Piper diagrams show that the samples mostly fall in high $\text{Ca} + \text{Mg}$ and $\text{SO}_4 + \text{Cl}$ fields indicating the water types and hydrogeochemical facies in the study area with few representations of water contaminated with gypsum. The overall chemistry of the water result in the study area shows that the quality of groundwater samples is fit for drinking and domestic uses based on WHO standards. Also, the majority of groundwater samples is fit for irrigation purposes.

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